

The Role of Health Benefits on the Performance of Employees in Kenya School of Law

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ABSTRACT

Without doubt, the most significant valuable asset for every company is its workforce. Retaining and satisfying staff is the hardest thing a business can do in today's cutthroat economy. Being a business owner means you have to find ways to cut expenses without sacrificing the quality of your net outcome. Therefore, although employers want more from their staff, employees also want more from them. Rewarding workers for putting out their best effort to come up with innovative ideas that improve company efficiency and further enhance both the financial and non-financial performance of the firm is one of the most effective ways to inspire employees. Kenya School of Law faces challenges pertaining rewards strategies due to inadequate budgetary allocation and prolonged policy development processes that have affected employee performance. Recently, Kenya School of Law reported reduced staff and staff dissatisfaction as among the reasons for not meeting its objectives. This thus justified the need as to why this study was carried out, with the aim to examine reward strategies and performance of employees in Kenya School of Law. The specific objective of the study was: to analyze effect of healthcare benefits on performance employees in Kenya School of Law. The study utilized a descriptive research design. The study targeted 155 respondents who are employees of the Kenya School of Law. The census approach was adopted as a result of the limited size of the research population. Both open and closed ended questions in questionnaire tool were employed to collect primary data from the respondents. Quantitative data was analyzed through descriptive statistics using Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 22 and Microsoft Excel and through inferential statistics mainly through multiple regression analysis. The study concludes that healthcare benefits should be taken into consideration since they had a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at the Kenya School of Law.

Key Words: Health Benefits, Employee Rewards. Employee Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

There is dire need for every organization to have good performance from its employees to accomplish its stated objectives. World over, organizations have reward strategies which they utilize to enhance employee performance which ultimately aims at improving organizational performance. Motivated individuals have no problem in taking greater duties when they are highly engaged and eager to complete their work (Bratton, 2007). Globally, majority of firms, on matters pertaining the hiring, retaining, and developing of personnel have become more crucial.

Organizations are constantly looking for strategies to keep their core personnel. According to Khan (2017), it has become quite usual for firms to use gain-sharing and profit-sharing plans, employee stock option plans, merit pay or performance-related compensation, and gain-sharing to entice the core workforce. There have been transition in most companies that previously looked for compliance and now they are looking for commitment; but this has prompted managers to consistently seek novel methods of providing incentive stimuli to foster self-regulated behavior among workers inside organizations. In fact, the key component of human resource (HR) strategy is the reward strategy (Khan, 2017). Workers are an organization's most valuable asset, and its ability to draw in, keep, and compensate highly skilled and competent workers will determine whether the firm succeeds or fails. The organization's incentive programs have a significant impact on employees' propensity to stick with their jobs (Boxall 2012).

It has been claimed that an organization's incentive structure influences how satisfied its workers are in their jobs and how willing they are to continue working in the organization. To ensure that workers perform at their best and are retained, organizations need to consider a variety of appropriate ways to show appreciation to them (Rowland & Hall, 2014). Rewards must be given top priority in any firm that wants to achieve its goals and objectives. It should go without saying that businesses that improperly handle this component of human resource management will negatively affect productivity and employee performance overall.

According to Herzberg's two factor theory, factors such as negative relationship between supervisor and co-worker, poor remuneration, poor working conditions and unfavorable company policies sometimes results in feel of dissatisfaction among employees. On the contrary, the elements that lead to staff contentment include responsibility, advancement in one's job, achievement, and acknowledgment. An organization that takes care of the needs of its employees and provides equal opportunities for career development has a better chance of achieving high performance since its employees are motivated and will perform well on their job tasks compared to one that does not (Tan, 2013).

In America and Europe reward systems started as early as 1950's based on Skinner's 1953 reinforcement theory that argues that employees' performance will increase with increase in rewards. He concluded that employees who are well rewarded will increase performance that brought the rewards. Maslow's theory on hierarchy of needs argues that employees' performance

is improved if their needs are met. The only way of meeting employee needs is through rewards. Countries in the Asian continent have equally used rewards to enhance the performance of employees (Thomas, Au, & Ravlin, 2019).

In 1970s, Nigeria began interest in effective rewarding to influence workers performance and motivate them. Concern of human resources experts on level of output attained from poor remuneration and motivation has been on increase as it affects performance of workers. Nwachukwu (2004) observed that teachers in Nigeria are not happy with their pay or working circumstances. Teachers there feel that they under paid as compared to other professionals, unconducive working environment, no decision making authority and no opportunity to develop their career.

In Kenya, there has been fast growth in the education sector guided by Kenya's vision 2030 policy document. This has resulted to establishment of many universities. This growth cannot be compared to the quality of graduates released into the Kenyan market Competitive salaries and benefits, can attract skilled educators to the profession and encourage experienced teachers to perform better.(Nyongesa and Bula, 2023). According to Marwa (2014), higher education institutions are getting increase in demands from stakeholders. There has been a lot of financial instability among higher institutions causing a lot of instability. This financial instability has affected the reward schemes resulting to industrial strikes (Waswa & Katana, 2018). Salaraies and other benefits tht are non financial are a major contributor to reducing labor turnover and improving performance of organizations (Bula, 2012).

1.1 Reward Strategies

Company performance is not only pegged on the monetary reward strategies but also on nonmonetary reward strategies for its employees. According to San, Theen and Heng (2012), nonmonetary rewards include staff development and training (open discussion on career path and routine trainings), individual growth (self-improvement programs), performance and recognition, career development opportunities (a fixed period of time to be promoted to the next level or opportunity to hold a managerial position), and positive workplace (such as spatial office) are admirable to employees and they subsequently improve employee performance in a firm.

According to Beardwell and Thompson (2014), performance appraisal is a performance measuring toolkit that gathers data on an individual's performance and compares it to previously established standards. According to DeNisi (2000), performance evaluations are a mechanism used by organizations in which workers are given ratings to compare their performance to predetermined goals in order to improve job performance. According to Fletcher (2001), the procedures used by businesses to assess employees in an effort to improve their performance, raise their competency, and give awards are referred to as performance appraisals.

Gupta (2018) states that performance appraisal assesses a worker's performance in a specific job to determine prospective areas of growth. Organizations carry out performance appraisal exercise on annual basis to determine employee contribution towards achieving organizational targets. According to Mutsuddi (2012), systematic procedure called performance evaluation is a formal exercise that is used to assess an employee's present performance and provide recommendations for future improvements so that the business and the individual can both benefit. Aspects such as quantity of work, time management, and quality of work among other agreed criteria are used in performance appraisal (Invancevich, 2003).

According to Mahapatro (2010), performance evaluations aid in decision-making regarding employment retention, job advancement, job transfer, bonus payments, pay increases, and enhance flow of information at all levels of employees. Performance appraisals enable employees to set personal objectives aligned to organizational goals and strive to achieve them. By emphasizing the value of excellent performance, performance appraisals aid in the creation of a performance culture inside an organization.

According to Govender and Bussin (2020), countries in South African regions have adopted several ways of ensuring employees have been rewarded that include the following; Pursuing fair play, which ensures rewarding is done fairly among employees without discriminating gender and ethnic groups. Avoidance of Economic Imbalance by ensuring wealth is distributed across upper and lower employee ranks. Others consist of insurance covers for diseases and injuries sustained at work, unemployment insurance or funds, and occupational health and safety, paternity leave, sick leave, study leave, sabbatical leave and family responsibility leave.

In Kenya, a number of acts have been enacted on labor relations, including the Works Injury Benefits Act (WIBA) of 2007, the Employment Act of 2007, and the Labor Institution Act of 2007.

The Labor Acts in Kenya Constitution clearly outlines; Hours and Pay regulations – normal working hours, overtime, night works, breaks, work on rest days, Public holidays, Sunday work, when public holiday falls on a Sunday and work during public holidays. Provisional for Annual leave. Minimum wage and other special leaves that includes, Maternity leave, paternity leave, preadoption leave, sick leave, compassionate leave, compulsory leave and leave of absence (Munyiva & Wainaina, 2018).

1.2 Kenya School of Law

The mission of the Kenya School of Law (KSL), founded in 1963, is to further legal education in Kenya. Under the Council of Legal Education (CLE) Act, the current KSL council was established in 1995 as a distinct statutory body with the sole objective of organizing and implementing training initiatives for the improvement of paralegals, government employees, and legal professionals. As it happens, the programs were designed primarily to get aspiring lawyers ready for the legal profession. In Kenya, a Ministerial Task Force was formed in 2005 with the goal of creating a legislative and policy framework for legal education and training. Reviewing the composition, structure, and functions of the KSL and the CLE was one of its mandates. Before becoming a semiautonomous government agency in July 2001, the School was a department of the Attorney General's Office. Following the recommendations by the task force that were later adopted, the scope and mandate of the KSL expanded from being a department to a full-fledged institution of training and legal education in Kenya. The Kenya School of Law Act 26 (2012) further reestablished the mandate of KSL to include: training of persons to be advocates; continuing professional legal development; provision of para-legal training; development of curricula and training manuals, conducting of examinations and conferment of academic awards; and undertaking research and consultancies among other functions (KSL report, 2019).

KSL is a significant organization that works for the public good in Kenya. Its primary clients include academic institutions, professional associations, civil society organizations, and agencies from the public and commercial sectors. Consequently, the performance of its employees is of great importance as it affects its overall performance and those that it serves. Therefore, there is need to assess how reward strategies affect the performance of employees in the KSL (KSL report, 2019).

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Both Public and private entities have a key role in economy ranging from various aspects. However, despite the major contributions, employees in these companies face challenges in reward strategies in form of performance appraisals, financial and non-financial rewards that affect their performance. Prior research has demonstrated a correlation between performance and reward (Kippra report, 2019).

The end-term evaluation and review of the strategic plan 2018-2022 by Kenya School of Law revealed a number of challenges of the firm, which affected the implementation of the plan activities. This resulted in unfulfilled key result areas in the KSL 2018 – 2022 strategic plan such as customer satisfaction and capacity development. General observation revealed that some of the challenges were because of inadequate staff and lack of motivation among the existing staff. There was awareness by management of the problem, which needed to be addressed and highlighted the same as a priority in their 2022 – 2028 strategic plans. However, it is worth noting that the reward strategy of KSL still remains the same and this is likely to continue being a source of dissatisfaction among its employees who may continue performing below par, consequently impacting the performance of KSL (KSL, report, 2019).

Obasan (2012) studied what affects compensation strategy on corporate performance. Study discovered there is a significant correlation between compensation strategies and the performance of workers, which has an effect on firm overall performance. Katua, Mukulu and Gachunga (2014) researched on the impact of HRM on Kenyan commercial banks' performance. The performance of commercial banks in Kenya following the study; is significantly improved by strategies for compensation, such as relations, and training and development. Additionally, it was shown that using both monetary and non-monetary incentives helped banks engage their staff, which in turn enhanced commitment and, ultimately, performance. The research indicates that employee performance in Kenyan commercial banks is positively correlated with strategic human resource management.

Muthengi (2017) investigated the impact of compensation plan on the performance of Kenya's Office of the Auditor General. There was an indication of a strong relationship between direct financial compensation and performance of employees while indirect financial motivation also

played a significant part in improving performance of employees, which translated to an improved firm performance.

Relationship between reward strategies and employee performance has received significant attention across the globe. The existing body of research examining the correlation between incentive strategy and employee performance has mostly concentrated on the private sector, with a notable absence of studies specifically targeting the public sector. There is therefore a need for the current study to fill the gap on the role of reward strategies on performance of employees based on a different context and sector.

The highlighted studies found a relationship between reward strategy and employee performance in different sectors and contexts with different outcomes. Numerous studies have been conducted to investigate the impact of reward strategy on employee performance. However, to date, no research has specifically examined the effects of reward strategy on the KSL. It is from this context this study researched on the KSL as a state corporation as it plays a crucial role in shaping legal education in Kenya. The research was conducted to ascertain the effectiveness of reward strategies on employee performance in Kenya School of Law and establish the relationship between variables.

3. OBJECTIVE

The objective of this study was to determine the effect of healthcare benefits on performance of employees in Kenya School of Law

4.LITERATURE REVIEW

4.1 Vroom's Expectancy Theory

This notion was postulated by Victor Vroom in 1964. Expectation theory holds that people put forth a lot of effort at work since they want to be rewarded. According to the theory, people initially join organizations with preconceived notions about their wants, motives, and prior experiences (Ngure & Waiganjo, 2017). Secondly, the theory presupposes that employees' actions stem from deliberate decision-making. As a result, employees have the freedom to make decisions at work. Thirdly, every employee can need different services from their employer. This explains why some workers are happy with their income while others are not. Finally, workers will choose the best

alternative that is accessible to them in order to maximize outcomes. Consequently, the anticipation of compensation from the best alternative at the employee's disposal will decide their level of job satisfaction. Yaseen (2013) states that the incentive may be extrinsic, like compensation and benefits, or intrinsic, like favourable working circumstances and recognition. Consequently, this hypothesis provides support for the notion that there exists a relationship between compensation plans and job satisfaction.

As stated by Miner (2015), expectation is the conviction of an individual that a specific behavior or course of action will lead to a desired consequence. The extent to which an individual thinks that their successful performance brings about the intended reward is known as instrumentality. On the other hand, valence refers to the likelihood that providing personnel with alluring rewards may increase production in addition to inspiring them. Put otherwise, valence is a measure of how strongly an employee prefers a certain result or reward (Flake, Barron, Hulleman, McCoach & Welsh, 2015).

According to Flake *et al.* (2015), rewards can be broadly classified into two groups: intrinsic rewards and extrinsic rewards. Meeting an employee's high demands, such as fostering their personal development and sense of self-worth, results in intrinsic rewards. The intrinsic motivations for the current study would be employee recognition and career progress. However, extrinsic benefits come from the organization and are not determined by the individual (Miner, 2015). The variable on employee benefits is supported by this theory.

4.2 Healthcare Benefits and Employee Performance

Kathure (2014) studied the effect of health benefits on employee loyalty at the KTDA. The sample size included 294 people in the population of interest. Because stratifying the population into groups was a simple process, the researcher employed stratified sampling. Self-administered questionnaires containing mix of closed-ended and open-ended items were employed to collect primary data for the study. Descriptive statistics were utilized in analyzing the gathered data. The study comes to the conclusion that management can utilize healthcare benefits as a technique to inspire staff members to work successfully and efficiently.

Waqas and Salem (2014) examined the effect healthcare benefits on employee engagement and firm performance in Faisalabad, Pakistan. Data from 250 participants was gathered using standardized surveys. The effect of rewards on business performance was assessed using

hierarchical linear regression with employee engagement acting as a moderating variable. The results demonstrated a strong correlation between company performance and healthcare benefits. The study, however, highlights a geographical gap as it was carried out on diverse firms in Pakistan while the current study concentrated on the Kenya School of Law in Kenya.

Bahari, Baharom Zahid and Daud (2022) undertook a research on effect of healthcare benefits on employee productivity with a focus on pharmaceutical companies in Turkey. The study target 289 workers at Eastpharma firm. Questionnaires were utilized to gather data. The study findings exhibited a positive correlation between team building and employee performance in a firm. The study concluded that, when healthcare benefits increases by one unit, employee productivity in Turkish companies will rise by 0.357 units when other factors that affect employee productivity remain constant. The study considered team building as a way of enhancing unity in a firm in order to enhance productivity. Meanwhile, the current study assessed the effect of healthcare benefits on employee performance.

Adom et al. (2020) studied how employee performance at a few chosen banks in Sunyani Municipality, Ghana, was impacted by healthcare benefits. Zinith bank and ADB bank were chosen for the study. Purposive simple random sampling was utilized to select 63 respondents from the two selected banks. The study's findings showed a strong correlation between healthcare benefits and workers' productivity in the banking sector. The study examined the effects of healthcare benefits on employee performance in the banking sector which a for profit sector while the current one examined the effects of healthcare benefits on employee performance in Kenya School of Law which is not for profit institution hence there is a contextual gap between the two.

Kipleting (2017) conducted a study at Eldoret Polytechnic in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya, to ascertain the effect of healthcare benefits on worker performance. A sample of 109 participants, selected by simple random selection, was employed in the study. Surveys were employed to gather data using semi-structured questionnaires. The study discovered that medical benefits have an effect on worker performance. The study concentrated on finding out the type of healthcare benefits existing at Eldoret Polytechnic while the current study evaluated the effect of healthcare benefits on employee performance, presenting a conceptual gap.

5. METHODOLOGY

5.1 Research design

The research design employed in the study was descriptive. Kim, Sefcik, and Bradway (2016) describe a descriptive study as any type of research that aims to comprehend the features of a specific group. For this study, the descriptive research approach was selected since it enables the questions of what, when, how, where, and who to be asked. The descriptive design encouraged the application of both quantitative and qualitative research methods so as to ascertain the effect of reward strategies on the performance of employees at the Kenya School of Law.

5.2 Target Population and sample size

Ngechu (2004) describes a population as a collection of people, products, services, essentials, or households that are the focus of an inquiry. The number of employees as of January, 2023 was 155 employees based on KSL employee establishment. The target audience for the research was all the 155 employees from all the categories comprising upper level, middle and lower-level employees. Table 1 shows employee categories at KSL.

Table 1: Category of employees at KSL

Category	Number
Upper cadre	10
Middle cadre	61
Lower cadre	84
Total	155

Source: Researcher (2023)

The research used census method given the small size of the study population. Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) assert that census method is appropriate when the study population is small, all of it can be included in a study. The researcher used this method in order to get an opportunity to collect enough information from all the members in the study population. Data collected using this method enabled the researcher to analyze it and arrive at more accurate results. The Kenya School of Law has 155 employees, which is a small population and therefore, all of the 155 employees were picked as the sample for the study.

5.3 Data collection

The study utilized questionnaires that included both open and closed-ended questions. The questionnaire was categorized into four main components: section one asked for demographic data, while sections two through four asked for descriptive data.

The researcher visited KSL in person and introduced herself to KSL. After outlining the aim of the research, the researcher asked for approval to carry out the planned investigation. The preexisting questionnaires were distributed to the participants for self-administration and then collected at a later time. This is called the drop-off and pick-up method where the researcher self-administers the questionnaires and picks them up at a later date (Clark & Finlay, 2007). Response rates have been demonstrated to rise using this strategy (Allred & Ross-Davis, 2011). The NACOSTI granted the researcher the research authorization that needed on time before starting the data collection process. The questionnaires were anonymous to ensure confidentiality of respondent information.

5.4 Data Analysis and Presentation

Savenye and Robinson (2004) state that data analysis is a way of explaining and demonstrating, summarizing and assessing, and evaluating data using statistical and/or logical methodologies. In this study, the researcher will obtain data from the field; subject it to editing before analyzing it. The data was coded and the codes analyzed through SPSS version 22 and Microsoft Excel. Data was analyzed through both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Means and standard deviations were utilized in descriptive analysis in determining population features. Multiple regression analysis was used in inferential statistics to establish the relationship between variables as shown below:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8 + \beta_9 X_9 + e \text{ Where:}$$

Y = Employee empowerment,

B₀ = Intercept

X₁ = Organization provides insurance cover

X₂ = Insurance covers other family members

X₃ = the sum insured is usually adequate for the year

X₄ = Insurance covers for dental issues

X₅ = Insurance covers for eye issues

X₆ = Insurance covers for eye issues

X₇= Insurance allows for acquiring medication in any hospital

X₈= Insurance covers maternity

X₉= Insurance enables employee longevity

B₁, β₂, β₃, β₄, β₅, β₆, β₇, β₈, β₉ are the coefficients of determination

Presentation of research findings was through tables, charts and graphs.

5.5 Ethical Considerations

Throughout the study period, the researcher conducted research in accordance with the rules, upholding the highest standards of research ethics. In order to demonstrate her status as an official student at Kenyatta University, the researcher requested an authorization letter from the school.

The respondents received assurances on the privacy and confidentiality of the data they submitted.

6. RESULTS

6.1 Response Rate

A cumulative number of 155 questionnaires were developed and sent out to respondents. Out of the 155 questionnaires, 138 were filled accurately and returned. The response rate is exhibited in Table 2.

Table 2: Response rate

Staff Category	Questionnaires distributed	Response rate	Percentage
Upper cadre	10	7	70
Middle cadre	61	55	90
Lower cadre	84	76	90
Total	155	138	89

Source: Survey data (2023)

The response rate findings show that, of the 155 targets, 138 responses were received, or 89% of the total. Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) indicate that in research, a response rate of 50% is satisfactory while one above 70 percent is excellent. This hypothesis led to the conclusion that an 89% response rate was excellent for the research problem's objective analysis.

6.2 Demographic Information of the Respondents

The aspects that were considered with regards to respondent demographic information included gender, age, level of education, employment category and number of years worked at the Kenya

School of Law. These personal employee characteristics were considered relevant to the study as they relate to their work. the demographic information is shown in table 3.

Table 3: Demographic Information

Demographics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	82	59%
Female	56	41%
Total	138	100%
Age		
18-25	13	9.4%
26-30	31	22.4%
31-40	42	30.4%
41-50	36	26.1%
Above 50	16	11.7%
Total	138	100%
Education		
Primary	2	1%
Secondary	13	9%
Certificate	19	14%
Diploma	26	19%
Undergraduate	48	35%
Postgraduate	30	22%
Total	138	100%
Employee Category		
Senior Staff	7	5%
Middle Staff	55	40%
Support Staff	76	55%
Total	138	100%
Number of years worked at KSL		
Less than 1 Year	13	9%
1-5	58	42%
6 and above	67	49%
Total	138	100%

Source: Survey data (2023)

Out of the 138 respondents, 82 (59%) were male while 56 (41%) were female. This indicates that the population of male employees at the Kenya School of Law is higher than that of female employees. The results show that the study included a representative sample of both male and female respondents, and that each gender's opinions were taken into account. These findings are

in line with a special report by Equileap which assessed workplace gender balance in the public sector and concluded that men make 57% of the workforce while women constitute 43%.

Those in the age bracket of 31 – 40 were the majority at 30.4% while those in the age bracket of 18 – 25 were the minority at 9.4%. Those in the age bracket of 26 – 30 include 22.4%, those in the age bracket of 41 – 50 were 26.1% while those above 50 years were 11.7% of the total respondents. This demonstrates that the staff composition at the Kenya School of Law includes personnel from varied age groups.

In educational attainment, 35% of the respondents had completed their undergraduate studies, while only a small percentage had completed their primary schooling. Those who had attained secondary level education stood at 9%, those with certificate 14%, those with diploma 19% and those who had attained postgraduate were 22%. There were 0% respondents with any other form of education. The results showed that the participants possessed sufficient literacy skills to furnish the needed data for the research. It also demonstrates that the study was not discriminatory in any way with regards to selecting study participants based on respondent level of education.

Majority of the respondents at the KSL represented by 55% were support staff followed by middle staff at 40% while the senior staff represented by 5% were the minority. This implied that perspectives regarding reward strategies and employee performance were collected from senior, middle and support staff.

Majority of the respondents represented by 49% had worked at the institution for 6 years and above followed by those who had worked at the institution for a period of between 1 and 5 years at 42% while those who had worked for a period of less than 1 year were the minority represented by 9%. This indicates that most of the participants had worked for the company for sufficient time to be acquainted with its reward strategies. This was also an indication that the study considered employees who had longer experience working at the institution as well as those with shorter experience.

6.3 Healthcare Benefits and Employee Performance

Respondents were requested to respond to several aspects regarding healthcare benefits in relation to employee performance at the Kenya School of Law as indicated in table 4.

Table 4: Healthcare benefits and employee performance

Statement	N	Mean	Std dev
Your organization gives a health insurance cover	138	4.02	0.41
The insurance covers other family members	138	3.19	0.45
The sum insured is usually adequate for a year	138	3.52	0.52
The insurance covers for dental issues	138	2.61	0.33
The insurance covers for eye issues	138	2.63	0.48
The insurance covers mental health issues	138	2.85	0.42
With the insurance cover you can go to any hospital for medication	138	2.73	0.46
The insurance covers for maternity issues	138	2.50	0.32
Employee longevity is made possible by life insurance.	138	3.81	0.48
Average mean score and standard deviation		3.10	0.43

Source: Survey data (2023)

The findings reveals that respondents strongly agreed with the statement that their organization gives a health insurance cover as evidenced by a mean of 4.02 with a std dev of 0.41. Respondents agreed that the insurance covers other family members as indicated by a mean of 3.19 and a std dev of 0.45 while a mean of 3.52 with a std dev of 0.55 indicated that respondents agreed with the statement that the sum insured is usually adequate for a year.

Respondents disagreed with the statements that the insurance covers for dental issues, the insurance covers for eye issues, the insurance covers mental health issues, with the insurance cover you can go to any hospital for medication, the insurance covers for maternity issues and that life employee longevity at the organization is made possible by life insurance as indicated by the means of 2.91, 2.63, 2.85, 2.73, 2.50 and 2.81 with standard deviations of 0.33, 0.48, 0.42, 0.46, 0.32 and 0.48 respectively.

An average mean of 3.10 is an indication that respondents moderately agreed that healthcare benefits at the Kenya School of Law are satisfactory. An average standard deviation of 0.43 indicates that the responses given were uniform. Based on the findings, employees at the Kenya School of Law are satisfied by the health benefits they are offered by the institution. The study findings are congruent with a study by Adom (2020) which indicated that employees tend to be

motivated by the healthcare benefits they receive. Another study by Kipleting (2017) found out that employees in a firm are affected by the type of healthcare benefits they receive. The study found out that employee performance improves as a result of desirable healthcare benefits to employees by the employer.

6.4 Multiple Regression

Multiple regression was carried out between the independent variables and the dependent variable to determine the relationship between them. This is shown in table 5.

Table 5: Multiple regression

Healthcare Benefits and Employee Performance			
Model Summary: R=0.932 R Squared=0.868 Adjusted R Squared=0.859			
ANOVA: F=93.881, p=0.000			
Variable	Coefficient	t-stat	sig
Constant	0.282	0.669	0.505
Organization gives a health insurance cover	0.142	2.013	0.046
The insurance covers other family members	0.021	0.271	0.787
The sum insured is usually adequate for a whole year	0.910	25.131	0.000
The insurance covers dental issues	0.013	0.211	0.833
The insurance covers eye issues	0.039	0.609	0.543
The insurance covers mental health issues	0.072	2.267	0.026
Insurance allows for acquisition of medication at any hospital	0.028	0.785	0.434
The insurance covers maternity	0.110	2.727	0.007
Employee longevity is made possible with the insurance	0.225	2.688	0.008

The value of adjusted R squared (0.859) indicates that 85.9% of the changes observed in employee performance were due to healthcare. The ANOVA F value and significance (F=93.881, p=0.000) indicated that the model was significant and that healthcare benefits could be used to determine employee performance. The constant was not significant indicating that on its own, healthcare benefits were of great impact to employee performance. Five of the nine variables were significant. A unit increase in the organization giving insurance health coverage, led to a 0.142 (p=0.046) increase in employee performance whereas a unit increase in the adequacy of the health coverage for the year would led to a 0.910 (p=0.000) increase in employee performance. Similarly, a unit increase in insurance cover for mental health issues, led to a 0.072 (p=0.026) increase in employee

performance. A unit increase in insurance cover for maternity led to a 0.110 (p=0.007) increase in employee performance. Finally, a unit increase in the perception of improvement of employee longevity due to insurance would lead to a 0.225 (p=0.008) increase in employee performance.

Thus the equation can be rewritten as:

$$Y=0.142x_1+0.910x_3+0.072x_6+0.110x_8+0.225x_9$$

7. CONCLUSION

From the results it was evident that health benefits were important to the employees and they increased employee performance in KSL. Providing health care alone was already significant to employee performance as was making sure that the health insurance was adequate for the whole year for the employees. Mental health and maternity cover were also found to be significant to employee performance indicating that these were some of the most pressing health issues that the employees wanted their employer to cater to. Overall, health benefits were found to improve the longevity of employees and this also improved the performance of employees.

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